

ICCM24
AUG 4-8, 2025 • BALTIMORE, MARYLAND

Advanced Graphene-Enhanced Polyethylene Liners for Type IV Hydrogen Storage Tanks: Enhancing Mechanical Properties and Gas Containment

J Jefferson Andrew, Jabir Ubaid, WJ Cantwell, KA Khan, R Umer

Department of Aerospace Engineering, Khalifa University, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
RIC2D, Khalifa University, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Background

Hydrogen as a clean energy carrier:

High specific energy (~3x gasoline by weight) and environmentally friendly

Challenges in storage due to low volumetric energy density in gaseous form

Hydrogen storage solutions:

Commonly stored as compressed gas at 700–900 bar in composite pressure vessels

Type IV vessels: polymer liner with carbon fiber overwrap for lightweight, strength, and gas containment

Polymer liner challenges:

Critical barrier against hydrogen permeation.

Subject to degradation from pressure cycles, temperature changes, and mechanical stress

Medium-Density Polyethylene (MDPE):

Widely used liner material due to ductility, chemical resistance, and ease of fabrication

Limitation: relatively high hydrogen permeability affecting long-term storage

Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs) as additives:

High aspect ratio and impermeability create tortuous paths reducing gas diffusion

Improve mechanical strength, stiffness, and impact resistance

Type IV Hydrogen Tank

Filament winding process

Objective of the Work

To systematically investigate the effect of incorporating graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) at 0.05–1 wt.% on medium-density polyethylene (MDPE) used as a liner material in Type IV hydrogen storage tanks.

To evaluate the impact of GNP addition on:

- Mechanical properties (tensile, flexural, and impact resistance)
- Thermal stability and crystallization behavior
- Gas barrier performance against gas permeation

To analyze the microstructure, filler dispersion, and polymer-filler interactions using advanced techniques such as Raman spectroscopy and 2D mapping.

To establish correlations between nanocomposite structure and macroscopic performance, providing guidance for optimizing liner materials in next-generation hydrogen storage systems.

Procedure

GNP

GNP + MDPE
+ Acetone
→
0, 0.05, 0.1,
and 0.5 wt. %

50°C

Oven

Fabricated Panels

Neat

0.05 wt. % GNP

0.1 wt. % GNP

0.5 wt. % GNP

130 °C
13 Mpa 2 hrs

Compression
Molding

Raman Mapping Analysis of GNP Dispersion in MDPE Composites

Confirmation of GNP Incorporation: G-band (1580 cm^{-1}), D-band (1350 cm^{-1}) & 2D-band (2700 cm^{-1}).

Control Comparison: Neat MDPE shows no graphitic peaks, validating GNP-specific signal origin.

Final Takeaway: Optimal GNP loading (**0.05–0.1 wt.%**) ensures structural integrity and **uniform dispersion** in MDPE composites.

Quasi-Static Mechanical Properties

- **0.05 wt.% GNP** raised **tensile load by 8.1%** and **stiffness by 3.7%** vs. neat MDPE.
- Higher GNP content (**>0.1 wt.%**) led to **agglomeration** and reduced strength.
- **Tensile ductility fell by 80.2%** from 114.4 mm to 22.7 mm at 0.5 wt.% GNP.
- **Flexural load** rose 23% and stiffness 19% at 0.05 wt.% GNP vs. neat MDPE.

Quasi-static test	Samples Shape	Samples Dimensions (mm)	Loading Speed (mm/min)
Tension	Dog-bone	33 (gauge length) × 6.35 × 3.5	5
3-Point Flexural	Rectangular	127 × 12.7 × 3.5	5

Dynamic Energy Absorption Characteristics

- Impact trends align with quasi-static results, optimal at 0.05 wt.%.
- **Neat MDPE** absorbed **30.76 J**; GNP helps only when well dispersed.
- **0.05 wt.% GNP** improved **peak force (+5%)** and **energy absorption (+3.6%)**.
- 0.05 wt.% GNP enhances energy dissipation mechanisms.
- **1 wt.% GNP** caused **26.5% drop** in peak force due to filler agglomeration.

- Striker: 12.7 mm hemispherical steel
- Impact energy: 50 J
- 5.45 kg mass
- Specimen size: 60 × 60 mm²

Thermal Analysis

- **0.05 wt.% GNP** raised melting temp (**T_m**) by **1.4%**; 0.1 wt.% raised it by 3.1%.
- T_m dropped slightly at 0.5 wt.% GNP, likely due to nanoparticle agglomeration.
- Crystallization temp (**T_c**) increased from **134.4 °C** to **~136.9 °C** for all GNP loads.

- Rise in T_c confirms GNPs act as nucleation sites during polymer cooling.
- Higher GNP loadings didn't further increase T_c, suggesting nucleation saturation.
- **Dual effect:** GNPs raise T_c via nucleation, and T_m via chain mobility restriction.
- Improved thermal transitions support **better stability** in hydrogen tank liners.

- DSC Sample mass: ~10 mg
- Heating range: 30 °C to 150 °C
- Heating/cooling rate: 10 °C/min
- Atmosphere: Nitrogen
- Cooling range: 150 °C to 30 °C

Thermomechanical Stability and Energy Dissipation Characteristics

- GNP-reinforced MDPE maintained **higher stiffness** across entire temp range.
- Loss modulus peaked ~ 140 MPa with GNP, 22% higher than neat MDPE (~ 115 MPa).
- Slightly lower $\tan \delta$ (0.216 vs. 0.218) suggests restricted chain mobility.
- **GNPs enhance toughness** without sacrificing stiffness or damping.
- DMA **confirms strong GNP–matrix interaction** and good nanoparticle dispersion.
- Even 0.05 wt.% GNP **boosts thermal-mechanical stability** significantly.

- Test mode: 3-point bending (25 mm span); Heating rate: 5 °C/min
- Specimen size: 30 × 12.5 × 3.5 mm³; Frequency: 1 Hz
- Temperature range: -40 °C to 100 °C

Gas Permeability test

- **0.05 wt.% GNP** significantly reduced gas permeability in MDPE sheets. GNP/MDPE showed slower pressure drop, indicating **lower gas diffusion rate**.
- GNPs create **tortuous pathways**, hindering gas molecule movement.
- Barrier effect stems from GNP's high aspect ratio and impermeability.
- Low filler loading still provides stable, **long-lasting diffusion resistance**.
- Enhanced gas resistance achieved **without sacrificing processability**.
- **Ideal for hydrogen tanks** where long-term barrier integrity is essential.

- Test gas: Helium
- Temperature: Room temperature (~25 °C)
- Pressure: Constant 10 bar
- Sample thickness: 0.5 mm

- The addition of GNPs significantly improved MDPE's multifunctional properties, with 0.05 wt.% identified as the optimal concentration. At this level:
 - Tensile strength and stiffness increased by 8.1% and 3.7%,
 - Flexural load and stiffness improved by 23% and 19%,
 - Low-velocity impact tests showed a 5.0% rise in peak contact force and 3.6% higher absorbed energy, indicating better dynamic load resistance.
- Raman spectroscopy and 2D mapping confirmed uniform dispersion at 0.05 wt.% (standard deviation = 0.05), while higher loadings caused agglomeration and reduced performance.
- Thermal analysis revealed: Increased melting point (from 108.5 °C to 111.9 °C)~2.5 °C rise in crystallization temperature due to nucleation
- DMA showed: 15.5% increase in storage modulus 21.7% increase in loss modulus, indicating improved stiffness and damping
- Helium permeability tests confirmed enhanced gas barrier performance due to well-dispersed GNPs.

These results establish low-GNP MDPE nanocomposites as strong candidates for Type IV hydrogen storage liners, combining mechanical strength, thermal stability, and impermeability.

Thank You

جامعة خليفة
Khalifa University

RiC2D